

TOPICAL ISSUES OF HOLDING EVENTS ORGANIZED BY DIPLOMATIC REPRESENTATIVES

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Abstract: The scientific thesis consistently reveals some forms of events organized by diplomatic representatives within the framework of cultural diplomacy. The relevance of this topic is obvious, because the practical implementation of these activities creates many issues not only of an organizational nature, but also of a material one. In this regard, the author came to the conclusion about the need to address these issues in the context of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Diplomatic representatives, events, festivals, cultural diplomacy, organizational events.

With the advent of the concept of "soft power", culture acts as an important resource of diplomacy used to promote the interests of the state, expand socio-cultural cooperation and improve mutual understanding between countries[1]. According to the true words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "it is important to popularize the historical and cultural heritage of cities and regions"[2], since "today we are moving on to the path of innovative development aimed at fundamentally improving all spheres of life of the state and society"[3].

According to scientists, "permanent cultural cooperation, support for heads of state and government based on mutual trust and good neighborliness, and the acceleration of these processes from year to year are the basis for enriching cultural diplomacy with new content"[4]. We fully agree with this opinion, considering it

necessary to add that cultural diplomacy is largely implemented by events organized by diplomatic representatives.

The following forms of cultural diplomacy are actively used in international relations: “forums, festivals, tours, exhibitions, fairs, days of the national language and culture, competitions, congresses, conferences, research and educational exchange programs, the practice of scholarships and grants, the activities of foundations . All these forms of international cultural exchange began to take shape a very long time ago, but only in the conditions of integration and internationalization did they receive the most complete and consistent development. [5].

In particular, diplomatic representatives may carry out the following activities:

- festivals;
- exchange of students of higher educational and other educational institutions;
- attracting foreign teachers to higher educational institutions;
- cultural events, conferences, etc.

The interest of the question posed lies in the fact that these events can be organized by diplomatic representatives (ambassadors) in the name of the execution of the presidential decree on strategic legal documents for the development of the state.

As scientists rightly point out, festivals have become platforms for mass communications, providing many opportunities to address the society of a particular state directly, bypassing state bodies, which was “one of the methods of public and diplomatic activity”[6].

But in practice, the organizers of these events are faced with problems of their financing. Often, financing issues remain completely unregulated, which may require sponsoring the organization of the event by means of volunteers or other organizations, which partially solves this problem, but may affect the independence

of the event, create risks of corruption, express individual interests at this event, which are not always can be correlated with the goals of the state policy pursued.

The holding of cultural events organized by diplomatic representatives is in demand for reasons of social, scientific and research factors. Let us give the following example of the organization of one of the festivals where the Ministry of Foreign Affairs was instructed:

- invite guests and participants of the Film Festival through the diplomatic missions of Uzbekistan abroad;
- invite representatives of the UN, CIS, SCO, FIAPF, diplomatic missions of foreign countries in Uzbekistan [7].

In carrying out this event, “the formation and approval by the Organizing Committee of the cost estimate for the preparation and holding of the Film Festival” was determined. It is noteworthy that other events initiated or carried out with the participation of diplomatic missions could be carried out following the model of this event.

From the study, the following conclusion can be drawn.

Conducting public and cultural diplomacy is vital and relevant, as it allows expanding the areas of interaction between society and the state, as well as foreign representatives with society in the Republic of Uzbekistan. These events can be considered an important form of social and political communication. To solve the problems of financing events held within the framework of public and cultural diplomacy, it is necessary to systematize the existing achievements in the legal regulation of festivals, conferences and other events held in Uzbekistan, and, based on this generalized analysis, develop the Regulation “On the organization and financing of public and cultural events held with participation of diplomatic missions and consular offices of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as diplomatic missions and consular offices of foreign states on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan”.

The adoption of this Regulation will bring more legal clarity to the organization and holding of these events, and will solve many problems related to

the financing of events organized by diplomatic missions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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